

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of the authors of the articles

Article	Gender	Profession	Location	Year of registration
A1	Woman	Front-end developer, software engineering student	Paris/São Francisco	2021
A2	Woman	Software Engineer	Berlin, Germany	2019
A3	Woman	Tech Lead/Senior Software Engineer	Washington	2020
A4	Woman	Software Engineer at Adobe	San Francisco, CA	2018
A5	Woman	Senior Backend Software Engineer	-	2018
A6	Woman	-	New York	2019
A7	Woman	Senior Android Developer	Helsinki, Finland	2019
A8	Woman	Developer	Ohio	2020
A9	Woman	Data Scientist/Software Engineer	Nairobi, Kenya	2021
A10	Woman	Software Engineer	Granada, Spain	2020
A11	Mixed	Engineers Group	Germany and Prague	2020
A12	-	Development	-	2019
A13	Woman	Developer	Seattle, Washington	2018
A14	-	-	-	2019
A15	Woman	JavaScript Developer	Nantes, France	2019
A16	Woman	Software Engineer	Bogotá, Colombia	2020
A17	Woman	Technical Content Writer	Seattle, Washington	2022
A18	Woman	-	Porto Alegre, Brazil	2021
A19	Woman	SAP Consultant/Tech Blogger	-	2020
A20	-	-	-	2023
A21	-	-	-	2019
A22	Woman	Senior Full Stack Developer	United Kingdom	2019
A23	Woman	Software Engineer	New York, New York	2020
A24	Woman	Information Security Specialist	Helsinki, Finland	2020
A25	Woman	Developer	London	2020
A26	Male	-	-	2019

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Article	Gender	Profession	Location	Year of registration
A27	-	-	-	2020
A28	Woman	Software Engineer	Berlin, Germany	2019
A29	Woman	Front-end/Full-stack Developer	Stockholm, Sweden	2020
A30	Woman	Software Engineer	-	2017
A31	Male	Senior Full Stack Developer	London	2019
A32	Woman	-	-	2018
A33	Woman	Senior Android Developer	Helsinki, Finland	2019
A34	Woman	Software Engineer	Berlin, Germany	2019
A35	Woman	Content and Community Manager	Hamburg	2020
A37	Woman	Researcher and Writer	-	2021
A38	-	London	2020	
A39	Male	Partner at Lightspeed Venture Partners	San Francisco, CA	2019
A40	Male	Software Engineering Intern	Colombo, Sri Lanka	2022
A41	Woman	Senior Front-end Developer	Dublin, Ireland	2020
A42	Woman	Business Systems Analyst	Los Angeles, California	2018
A43	Woman	Developer Experience Engineer	The Hague	2019
A44	Woman	Development Manager	Victoria, British Columbia	2019
A45	Male	Independent Consultant	-	2012
A46	Male	Editor-in-Chief, Culture and Methods	-	2009
A47	Male	Agile Coach	-	2018
A48	Male	Editor-in-Chief, Culture and Methods	-	2009
A49	Woman	Agile Coach	-	2016
A50	Woman	Engineering Manager	-	2023
A51	Male	Independent Consultant	-	2012
A52	Male	Independent Consultant	-	2012
A53	Woman	CTO	China	2022
A54	Woman	Software Developer	-	-
A55	Woman	Leadership Development Expert	San Francisco	-

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Article	Gender	Profession	Location	Year of registration
A56	Woman	Various Roles in AI and Blockchain	-	-
A57	Woman	Film Producer	-	-
A58	Woman	Agile Coach	-	-
A59	Woman	Programmer	-	-
A60	Woman	Agile Coach	-	-
A61	Male	Independent Consultant	-	2012
A62	Woman	Engineering Leader	-	-
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